

MEDICAL SCIENCES

PHOTODYNAMIC THERAPY IN THE TREATMENT OF CARIES

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Abstract

The article presents the results of a literature review on the problems of the prospects for using photodynamic therapy in the treatment of caries. A comparison was made of the possibilities of replacing traditional medicinal treatment of a carious cavity with photodynamic therapy and the advantages of this method were determined.

Keywords: caries, drug treatment, photodynamic therapy, photoactivated disinfection.

Despite the high level of development of technologies in general and dental technologies in particular, many controversial issues remain about the methods and stages of dental treatment. In the section of dentistry, which is devoted to the problem of caries, there is also a large number of various, completely unresolved problems. There have been a significant number of theories about the causes leading to the development of caries for many years, which have changed over time depending on the state of scientific progress. The modern, generally accepted mechanism for the occurrence of caries is the progressive demineralization of hard dental tissues under the influence of organic acids, the formation of which is associated with the activity of microorganisms. Long-term restoration using modern materials. The principles of treatment in all of the above methods are similar; they boil down to cleansing the carious cavity from pathologically altered tissues, drug treatment and the filling itself. However, the issue of drug treatment of the cavity before filling has not been resolved unambiguously. Medical treatment of carious cavities is an important stage in preparing a tooth for filling. The main objectives of medicinal treatment of carious cavities are: - cleaning the cavity from oral fluid and other contaminants; - bactericidal effect on the microflora located in the void and parietal dentin; - drying the cavity; for medicinal treatment, must meet the following series of requirements:

- do not stain unaltered tooth tissues;
- do not have a toxic effect on the pulp;
- do not have carcinogenic properties;
- do not overdry the tooth tissue;
- do not impair the adhesion of the filling material to the walls of the cavity; sterility of the cavity before filling.

For a long time, solutions of potent antiseptics were used for the medicinal treatment of carious cavities, for example: phenol, 3% hydrogen peroxide solution, 96° alcohol, and the cavity was dried with medical ether. To avoid pulp irritation, deep cavities were washed with warm solutions of weak antiseptics: 1%

hydrogen peroxide, 1% chloramine solution, 0.1% furatsilin solution.

Over time, approaches to medical cavity treatment have changed significantly. It is not recommended to use alcohol and ether for treating cavities due to toxicity and the ability to dry out dentin. In addition, there are concerns that alcohol and ether may reduce the adhesion of materials. Currently, when filling for the purpose of medicinal treatment, it is recommended to use irrigation of the cavity with warm antiseptics of low concentrations from a syringe. For these purposes, use a 3-5% solution of sodium hypochlorite, 0.06 0.1% solution of chlorhexidine, 3% solution of hydrogen peroxide, 0.02% solution of furatsilin, etc. The cavity is dried using a stream of air from a "gun" or a sterile cotton ball. It should be recognized that treatment in this way, firstly, is not effective enough, and secondly, it is technologically complex (the use of cofferdam and a "vacuum cleaner" is necessary); some of the listed drugs have a very unpleasant taste of isapah (sodium hypochlorite) and require immediate removal from oral cavity. inhibit the polymerization process of the composite adhesive system, disrupting the properties of the "hybrid layer". Since its inception, photodynamic therapy has penetrated into the medical industry: oncology, surgery, gynecology and others. PDT) is considered to be photoactivated disinfection (FAD). FAD is used in the treatment of caries and its complications, in periodontics and diseases of the oral mucosa. The mechanism of action of PDT is that positively charged photosensitizer molecules selectively attach to the walls of negatively charged pathogenic bacteria. -gives peak absorption of the photosensitizer, leads to activation of the reagent and the formation of atomic (singlet) oxygen, which destroys the walls of bacterial, fungal and viral cells, leading to their death. From the above it follows that to carry out FAD, a photosensitizer and a range source (most often a laser) are necessary. A photosensitizer is a natural or artificially synthesized substance capable of photosensitizing biological tissues,

that is, increasing their sensitivity to light. Photodynamic therapy. Research has proven that under the influence of photodynamic therapy, such groups of microorganisms are completely destroyed.

- Streptococcus sanguis, Streptococcus mutants, Streptococcus sab-rinus;
- Fusobacterium nucleatum;
- Actinobacillus actinomycetemcomitans, Actinomyces viscosus; ureus;
- Candida albicans;
- Klebsiella pneumonia;
- Escherichia coli;

By using a low-energy laser as a radiation source, microcirculation in the pulp is activated due to the properties of coherent low-intensity radiation. -water/air type; – the laser is activated at a power of 100–200 mW and for 60 seconds. The surface of the carious cavity treated with a photosensitizer is illuminated.

Conclusions.

The use of this technology makes it possible to obtain the following results: a 1.30-second exposure to PDT leads to a reduction in pathogenic flora in carious cavities by 40%. ation in the dental pulp due to increased regulatory effects on microvessels, which leads to normalization of blood flow in the microvasculature. on infected hard dental tissues, which contributes to a more complete elimination of microorganisms, improved adaptation of the filling material and prevention of the development of secondary caries, as well as activation of microcirculation in the pulp.

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